

Project Summary

As the volume of publicly accessible federally funded research outputs increases, the ability to comprehensively report on the impact and usage of such outputs becomes increasingly challenging. Usage and impact data pertaining to a single publicly accessible book, article, or dataset are created across a complex array of public and private publishers, publication distributors and aggregators, discovery services and service platforms. Access to comparable, high-quality information is vital to CRIS (research information management) systems, impact reporting, and innovation policy; and is inherent to implementing the Open Research Funders Group vision where open scholarship impact statements are included alongside data management plans in grant proposals and reporting. Yet, compiling usage and impact metrics across public and private repositories, services, and publishers is a time and data-science expertise intensive activity undertaken by individual researchers, universities, libraries, and publishers. While services provision publicly available usage data sources, challenges related to security, neutrality, and trust confront the aggregation of commercially derived usage data sources.

The European Data Strategy is fostering “data spaces” to facilitate interoperable, federated, secure data exchange and processing for specific industries. There are broad opportunities for application. For example, the OA Book Usage Data Trust (OAEBUDT) effort funded by the Mellon Foundation applies the model to the secure, ethical aggregation, provision and benchmarking of public and sensitive, proprietary usage generated by commercial publishers and distributors. To prepare for the shift to public access of scholarly outputs, scholarly communications stakeholders aim to explore shared cyberinfrastructure interests and requirements related to public access reporting and compliance. Core to this infrastructure are the structures and tools through which impact (engagement and use) are measured.

This proposal requests support to host a facilitated workshop of 30 stakeholders before the 2023 Coalition for Networked Information Spring Member Meeting. The workshop will invite international experts and leading scholarly cyberinfrastructures to: a) identify challenges to cross-platform public and open impact analytics at scale, b) explore open infrastructure opportunities to improve the FAIRness of usage data, and c) identify what’s needed to scaffold America’s national infrastructure for scholarly output impact reporting in light of the Nelson memo and the European Open Science Cloud Core and Interoperability Framework. Challenges related to public access impact reporting of data, articles, and books will be considered alongside anticipated issues related to complex, expansive, and emerging digital publications that may include simulations, 3D models, datasets, videos, and other multimedia. Workshop findings will be documented in a report that will be distributed through public repositories.

Intellectual Merit

This workshop gathers stakeholders to advance four strategic collaboration opportunity areas that surfaced in a November 2022 ARL survey of research data organizations, specifically addressing how to facilitate economies of scale related to the reporting and analysis of usage data related to publicly accessible scholarship outputs. Publicly accessible conference proceedings will inform future collaborations among policy-makers, scholars of science policy, and cyberinfrastructure researchers by: 1) informing service and technical roadmaps of core infrastructure related to public access impact reporting, 2) surfacing opportunities for collaboration and efficiencies among cyberinfrastructure efforts, and 3) identifying potential future collaborative or translational projects.

Broader Impacts

In bringing together key stakeholders in public-access related usage and impact reporting who currently work in separate silos to focus on the efficacy and future of FAIR research impact reporting, this project can identify ways to build economies of scale for institutional reporting while also identifying ethical concerns related to the aggregation and use of scholar-specific impact data in an automated fashion at the global scale.